

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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During preschool childhood, profound changes occur in a child's thinking. A preschooler begins to distinguish the properties of surrounding objects, understand the simplest connections between them, and use these connections in his manipulations. This creates the necessary conditions for further mental development, is associated with the development of elementary forms of play and drawing, and speech.

In children of this age, at the initial stages of development, due to their limited experience and insufficient ability to use thinking operations, thinking often turns out to be too simple, not corresponding to reality. Seeing how a plant is watered, a child comes to the conclusion that “it is necessary to water a teddy bear so that it grows better.”

A child of middle preschool age can observe relatively complex thinking, in which he carefully takes into account all new information found in the process of solving a problem.

The brain of a preschooler is mobile and flexible, open to new knowledge. Therefore, good habits, a desire to engage in sports, music, theater and fine arts are formed in preschool children.

There are several factors that have a strong influence on a child's thinking:[1]

- Communication circle. The older the child, the more children and adults there should be around him. Kindergartens, clubs and sections help in this. The child should observe the various behaviors of adults and children.
- Speech development. The child learns to build sentences, express his thoughts.
- Formation of an analytical worldview. Preschool children are distinguished by their attention to shapes, color, size, spatial location and time intervals.
- Acquisition of skills and abilities. The child learns to tell stories, read syllables, sing songs.

- Formation of personal qualities. Character, flexibility, initiative, organization - all this is formed as a result of educational activities.
- Formation of self-esteem. A developed child is able to evaluate himself.
- The emergence of self-control. The child learns to control his behavior and actions.

Analyzing the process of thinking in preschool age, many authors, based on the specificity and importance of this stage in the life of an individual, agree that thinking at this period should be considered in conjunction with the mental development of a preschool child.

Studies have shown that older preschool children, using the system of socially developed emotional standards they have mastered, master some rational methods of examining the external properties of objects. Their use allows the child to perceive and analyze complex objects in a differential way[2].

Preschool children can understand the general connections, principles, and laws underlying scientific knowledge. For example, at the age of 6-7, a child is able to learn not only individual facts about nature, but also knowledge about the interaction of the organism with the environment, the form and function of an object, needs and behavior, and their interrelationships. However, preschool children achieve a sufficiently high level of cognitive activity if activities are aimed at the active development of thinking processes and are directed to the “zone of proximal development”[3].

The basis of the development of thinking is the formation and improvement of mental actions. It depends on what mental actions the child performs, what knowledge he acquires and how he uses them. Thus, the mastery of mental actions in preschool children occurs according to the general law of assimilation and internalization of externally directed actions.

List of used literature

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